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WEMSAR

WIND ENERGY MAPPING USING SYNTHETIC APERTURE RADAR

EUROPEAN COMMISSION FIFTH FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME

ENERGY, ENVIRONMENT AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

KEY ACTION 5: CLEANER ENERGY SYSTEMS, INCLUDING RENEWABLE ENERGIES

DATA ACCESS, SAR WIND ENERGY RETRIEVAL VALIDATION

DELIVERABLE D3 AND D4

WEMSAR REPORT NO. 2

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Executive Summary

This report gives a description of available SAR data (D3) and the SAR wind retrieval validation work (D4) of the WEMSAR project.

With high-resolution SAR images, which have been available from satellites since 1991, it is possible to estimate ocean wind fields in coastal regions with a resolution of a 400m. It is very important that correct calibration is performed so radar backscatter relates to the sea surface properties, and not to instrument instability and range related effects. The CMOD-IFR2 algorithm has been used to derive wind maps from 84 ERS SAR images from the three defined test sites in Norway, Denmark and Italy (and Egypt). The disadvantage of SAR wind retrievals using C-band models is the requirement for wind direction as an input to the algorithm. For the present study we first calculated the SAR wind maps using a single wind direction from in situ data. To improve these first calculations, we then used a FFT technique to derive wind direction directly from the SAR image (Gerling, 1986; Vachon and Dobson, 1996). The SAR scene is divided into 8×8 sub-images from which the image spectra are derived using two-dimensional FFT. From the direction of the peaks in the long wavelength part of the spectrum (wavelengths longer than 1500 m) wind directions with an ambiguity of 180° are estimated. The ambiguity in the wind direction estimate is solved by the use of weather maps or *in situ* data. The estimated wind direction in the sub-images are interpolated to the whole scene and used as input to the CMOD-IFR2. In the cases where a wind direction was retrieved in less than three of the 64 sub-images, the in situ wind direction was used. The accuracy of the FFT technique is estimated to about 20° in the cases where wind streaks are present (Vachon and Dobson, 1996).

SAR derived wind have then been compared with in situ wind measurements and some model results, and the overall capability of SAR to estimate wind speeds in coastal regions assessed.

Tables listing the SAR data and in situ measurements are given first, followed by the validation section. Then, 3 appendices show the SAR wind maps from the three test sites. In a final appendix, a paper by Furevik and Espedal (2001) is included. In this paper (accepted for publication), the preliminary validation of the Hellisøy test site in Norway will be published in Canadian Journal of Remote Sensing.

A CD-Rom with the SAR data, is also included as part of deliverable D3.

Project summary

Objectives

The overall objective is to investigate, validate and demonstrate the potential of satellite-based synthetic aperture radar (SAR) to map wind energy in offshore and near-coastal regions for potential wind turbine siting. The value of the SAR observations can be enhanced in combination with scatterometer, altimeter, model information and in situ data.

The WEMSAR tool will introduce satellite radar data into a system for selecting optimum locations for wind turbine parks. This will provide high spatial resolution wind information for wind turbine siting, and thus improve cost-effectiveness when developing the renewable wind energy source. WEMSAR will also improve the exploitation of Earth Observation data.

Description of the work

The project consists of the following work packages;

- Implementation of existing algorithms for wind data retrieval from satellite radars, based on a literature search.
- Satellite data from SAR, altimeter and scatterometer will be obtained, processed and analysed, and wind information obtained. Validation of SAR wind energy retrieval capabilities will be performed.
- The micro-siting model will be tuned for optimal integration in the WEMSAR tool.
- Development of an integrated WEMSAR tool for optimum data synergy for maximum site selection efficiency. The tool will include information from mesoscale and micro-siting models, and satellite data. Integration with computer models covering land and topography, and integration in a Geographic Information System (GIS) will be tested. The tool will be streamlined according to user requirements.
- WEMSAR validation. For three test sites a WEMSAR wind atlas will be produced and compared against in situ data.
- Production of a marketing plan including a cost/benefit assessment for identifying potential customers, where the customers operate and the time frame of their projects. This task includes planning and initiation of product exploitation.

Expected Results and Exploitation Plans

The development of the WEMSAR tool and testing in three test sites. Results should demonstrate the usefulness of the proposed tool and provide valuable information for cost-effective planning of wind energy production sites.

The project web site is: <http://www.nrsc.no/WEMSAR>.

WP2: Data access, SAR wind energy retrieval validation

Task objective: To collect and analyze satellite radar and on site data from the case study sites (Norway, Denmark and Italy). This will be used to validate the application of high spatial resolution wind energy retrieval from satellite-based SAR.

Background

Using the SAR toolbox (available online at: <http://earth.esa.int/STBX/>), the ERS SAR PRI scenes have been calibrated in order to obtain optimal wind speed estimates from the empirical C-band model. The wind speed in this study was retrieved from the normalised radar backscatter cross section using the CMOD-IFR2 algorithm developed at the Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer, Brest, France (IFREMER). This algorithm is empirically tuned to buoy measurements and is used operationally for retrieval of wind fields from the ERS Wind Scatterometer (WSC). Investigations have shown that in contrast to the SAR Wind Algorithm (SWA) using azimuth cut-off (Vachon *et al.*, 1994), the SAR wind speed estimates using C-band models appear not to be affected to the same degree by fetch-limited sea. However, the atmospheric conditions and surface film presence may affect the results (Kerbaol *et al.*, 1998; Korsbakken *et al.*, 1998). The CMOD-IFR2 is developed for neutral stability and errors will therefore be introduced in SAR wind speed estimates if conditions are unstable or stable. Atmospheric conditions are also important for the interaction of the air flow with the topography. On days with low-level temperature inversion, the air can be forced around topographical obstacles and generate jets and gap winds in certain localities (Pan and Smith, 1999; Sandvik and Furevik, 2001). While on other days the flow can receive a speed-up effect from the topography, giving higher wind speeds at the top of hills. Unfortunately, no temperature profiles are available to investigate this further in the data set presented for Hellisøy here (in situ measurements from land-based lighthouse).

The SAR wind speeds are retrieved for a pixel size of $400\text{m} \times 400\text{m}$, as wind information for use in coastal areas must be of high spatial resolution, and the quality of such data must be validated. Wind speed estimates from SAR are comparable to the WSC wind speeds, and the spatial variability in the SAR estimates only increases slightly with higher resolution (down to a pixel size of $500\text{ m} \times 500\text{ m}$) compared to the coarse WSC estimates (Furevik and Korsbakken, 2000). However, between $500\text{ m} \times 500\text{ m}$ to $200\text{ m} \times 200\text{ m}$ in pixel size the variability of the SAR retrieved winds increased significantly. Korsbakken *et al.* (1998) show plots for the mean values of SAR retrieved wind in sub-images around a ship position for varying sub-image size (100m to 10km). In this study it was concluded that the SAR winds did not change significantly with the sub-image area size. Profiles drawn in SAR wind maps of $400\text{ m} \times 400\text{ m}$ pixel size, do not show sign of speckle when compared to ship track data (Furevik *et al.*, 2001).

A disadvantage of SAR wind retrievals using C-band models is the requirement for wind direction as an input to the algorithm. For the present study we first calculated the SAR wind maps using a single in situ measurement (for each image). To improve these calculations, we then used the FFT technique (Gerling, 1986; Vachon and Dobson, 1996). The SAR scene is divided into 8×8 sub-images from which the image spectra are derived using two-dimensional FFT. From the direction of the peaks in the long wavelength part of the spectrum (wavelengths longer than 1500 m) wind directions with an ambiguity of 180° are estimated.

The peaks in an image spectrum are orthogonal to the wind streaks often observed in SAR data. Wind streaks are surface manifestations of atmospheric roll vortices or Langmuir cells, and are aligned with the local wind direction (Alpers and Brummer, 1994; Brown, 1980). The ambiguity in the wind direction estimate is solved by the use of weather maps or *in situ* data. The estimated wind direction in the sub-images are interpolated to the whole scene and used as input to the CMOD-IFR2. In the cases where a wind direction was retrieved in less than three of the 64 sub-images, the *in situ* wind direction was used. The accuracy of the FFT technique is estimated to about 20° in the cases where wind streaks are present (Vachon and Dobson, 1996). For a given error in wind direction, the largest error in wind speed is found for high radar return. However, for strong winds the variation in local wind direction is small, and in almost all these cases wind streaks are present in the SAR scenes. For 23° incidence angle of the ERS SAR, an error in wind direction of 50° for a backscatter value of -6dB would result in an error in wind speed of up to 3 m/s in the CMOD-IFR2 algorithm (depending on wind direction relative to the satellite flight direction).

The resulting wind speed matrices can be transformed into matrices of wind energy (energy flux) by applying the bulk formula (see e.g. a basic physics book such as Marion and Hornyak, 1982):

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \rho_{air} V^3, \quad (1)$$

where E [W/m^2] is the energy flux, ρ_{air} [kg/m^3] is the density of the air and V [m/s] is the wind speed. The density for dry air is $1.225 kg/m^3$ at standard pressure and a temperature of 15°C. From this relation it is clear that low wind speeds contribute very little to wind energy relative to medium and high wind speeds. For very high wind speeds, the rotor blades risk being damaged due to turbulence and the turbines are normally switched off. However, for technical design of the wind turbines, knowledge of extreme/very high winds is required since the turbines have to withstand these winds. In the working range of the wind turbines, high winds give most wind energy. However, these events are more seldom (low frequency of occurrence), and therefore medium winds are usually the most important for wind energy production.

WP2.1: Radar data – Deliverable 3 (D3)

The data obtained and analysis work performed are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Data and work performed in WP2.

Location	Nbre. of SAR scenes	SAR wind retrieved	In situ data obtained	Model results obtained	Validation performed
Norway, Hellisøy	50	completed	yes	partially	partially
Denmark, Horns Rev	20	completed	yes	yes	yes
Italy, Maddalena	9	completed	yes	partially	partially
Egypt, Gulf of Suez	5	completed	yes	yes	partially

Hellesøy, Western Norway

The 50 SAR scenes acquired for this test site have been calibrated and wind retrieved. The CMOD-IFR2 requires input wind direction to calculate wind speed from the SAR imagery. First, the input wind direction was obtained from the in situ measurements. Then all the wind maps were re-calculated in order to obtain wind direction directly from the SAR imagery whenever possible (when wind streaks are present). The data are described in Table 2. In situ measurements are taken from Helligsøy lighthouse and SAR wind (for comparison) taken from a 10km×10km box outside Helligsøy.

Table 2. Helligsøy data.

- In situ wind from **Helligsøy** lighthouse at Latitude 60°45'. Longitude 4°43' (33m above sea level) (Measurements from hour nearest imaging taken).
- **SAR wind** extracted in 10km × 10km box outside Helligsøy (10m above sea level). Wind direction taken directly from SAR image whenever possible (FFT techniques), otherwise Helligsøy wind direction used. (Those scenes without SAR wind speed do not cover the 10km × 10km box).

(Wdir is always given relative to north).

No.	DATE	Time (UTC)	Orbit	Frame	Wdir. Helligsøy [deg.]	WS Helligsøy (at 33m) [m/s]	Wdir. SAR [deg.]	WS SAR [m/s]	Comments
1	960126	2128	23707	1215	32	5.2	-	1.5	Too little open ocean
2	960203	1049	23815	2374	1.0	5.5	-	6.2	To little wind
3	960214	2131	23979	1215	199	18.1	212.8	9.3	
4	960215	2131	04306	1215	238	1.6	-	2.6	Too varying wind
5	960222	1052	24087	2367	159	10.1	-	-	Swells ???
6	960222b	1052	24087	2385	159	10.1	147.8	5.1	
7	960309	1049	24316	2374	86	3.1	-	0.9	Too little wind
8	960310	1049	04643	2385	182	8.7	154.3	6.4	
9	960405	2128	24709	1215	150	6.3	-	3.3	Too little open ocean
10	960406	2128	05036	1215	70	1.9	-	0.0	Too little open ocean
11	960413	1049	24817	2374	269	2.7	-	0.2	Too little wind
12	960430	1047	05373	2385	338	11.2	325.3	4.5	
13	960519	1049	05645	2385	110	7.6	57.2	4.9	
14	960604	1047	05874	2385	180	11.1	152.0	3.3	
15	960617	2134	25754	1215	315	6.0	309.3	4.9	
16	960622	1049	25819	2374	339	14.7	8.9	10.3	
17	960623	1049	06146	2374	321	8.5	327.6	4.3	
18	960704	2131	06310	1222	190	5.0	-	2.9	Too little wind Weather maps
19	960719	2128	26212	1215	189	4.4	-	1.2	Too little wind
20	960727	1049	26320	2374	234	9.3	228.9	7.0	
21	960808	2131	06811	1215	146	4.3	123.0	1.4	

22	960901	1049	07148	2374	211	2.9	-	0.1	Too little wind
23	960912	2131	07312	1215	7	8.9	-	7.4	
24	961006	1049	7649	2374	225	10.2	-	6.7	No streaks.
25	961022	1047	07878	2385	199	7.7	149.7	2.8	
26	961110	1049	08150	2374	113	6.1	147.4	6.1	Wrong in Sognefjord
27	961129	1052	08422	2367	106	10.4	-	-	
28	961129b	1052	08422	2385	106	10.4	114.8	9.4	
29	961215	1049	08651	2374	27	2.7	33.3	5.6	
30	970103	1052	08923	2367	106	6.4	-	-	Need in-situ data
31	970103b	1052	08923	2385	106	6.4	-	-	
32	970119	1049	9152	2374	102	2.6	-	2.5	Too little wind
33	970204	1046	09381	2385	278	13.1	-	2.9	Too little wind
34	970207	1052	09424	2367	236	15.2	-	-	
35	970207b	1052	09424	2385	236	15.2	236.4	9.7	
36	970223	1049	9653	2374	175	22.9	173.8	15.0	Not clear wind streaks.
37	970325	2134	10089	1215	193	8.7	197.8	8.4	
38	970330	1049	10154	2374	243	9.3	237.9	7.6	Not clear wind streaks.
39	970504	1049	10655	2374	4	4.7	44.1	2.1	
40	970603	2134	11091	1215	347	11.7	29.8	5.9	
41	970608	1049	11156	2374	118	8.1	145.4	0.6	
42	970627	1052	11428	2367	339	6.4	-	-	Wdir from Helligsøy
43	970627b	1052	11428	2385	339	6.4	-	3.6	Wdir. From Helligsøy
44	970713	1049	11657	2374	180	3.9	-	1.6	Too little wind
45	970817	1049	12158	2374	180	7.6	-	5.5	No streaks
46	970902	1046	12387	2385	-	-			Need weather maps
47	970905	1052	12430	2385	202	16.0	220.0	7.1	Helligsøy at 14.00UTC
48	970905b	1052	12430	2367	202	16.0	-	-	Helligsøy at 14.00UTC
49	970921	1049	12659	2374	293	4.6	-	4.5	No streaks
50	971021	2134	13095	1215	260	9.7			

In addition, a preliminary comparison of the SAR wind fields have been performed against model results from ECMWF (see validation section). The SAR wind maps are collected on a CD-Rom labelled WEMSAR-Deliverable D3. The wind maps are shown in Appendix A.

Horns Rev, Western Denmark

The 20 SAR scenes acquired for this test site have been calibrated and wind retrieved. The CMOD-IFR2 requires input wind direction to calculate wind speed from the SAR imagery. First, the input wind direction was obtained from the in situ measurements. The all the wind maps were re-calculated in order to obtain wind direction directly from the SAR imagery

whenever possible (when wind streaks are present). The data are described in Table 3. In situ measurements are taken from an offshore mast.

Table 3. Horns Rev data.

*In situ wind from meteorological tower at Horns Rev at 62m height (Latitude 55°31'. Longitude 7°49'). Time approx. 1030UTC or 2130UTC for SAR and in-situ both.

**Wind direction taken directly from SAR image whenever possible (FFT techniques), otherwise met. tower wind direction used.

(Wdir is always given relative to north).

No.	Date	Time (UTC)	Orbit	Frame	Wdir in-situ* [deg.]	WS-in-situ* [m/s]	Comments
1	000116	1030	24783	2475	305.6	11.5	Front passage, atm. Gravity waves
2	000116b	1030	24783	2493	305.6	11.5	Wind streaks
3	000201	1030	25012	2493	235.1	15.6	
4	000307	1028	25513	2475	256.3	17.6	Wind shift at a front
5	000307b	1028	25513	2493	256.3	17.6	
6	000516	1028	26515	2493	182.3	8.3	Low winds
7	000516b	1028	26515	2475	182.3	8.3	Wind streaks parallel to shore.
8	000326	1031	25785	2475	125.6	4.8	
9	990520	2130	21340	1107	122.3	8.2	Gravity waves. No clear wind streaks.
10	990621	2124	21798	1107	313.9	11.2	Wind streaks
11	990710	2127	22070	1107	71.8	7.3	Static stable stability ? More wind south of Horns Rev.
12	990729	2130	22342	1107	34.9	7.6	Wind streaks are not clear.
13	990810	1028	22507	2493	328.8	12.2	Wind streaks. Local wind fronts.
14	990830	2124	22800	1107	291.8	08.1	Clear wind streaks
15	991003	1030	23280	2475	240.8	13.8	Clear wind streaks. Rain cells.
16	991003b	1031	23280	2493	240.8	13.8	
17	991007	2130	23344	1107	274.4	12.3	Rain cells and gusts.
18	991019	1028	23509	2493	88.8	9.4	Some lee effects.
19	991123	1028	24010	2493	233.3	3.0	Low wind.
20	991216	2130	24346	1107	244.3	13.5	Drop in wind speed towards shore..

The SAR wind maps are collected on a CD-Rom labelled WEMSAR-Deliverable D3. The wind maps are shown in Appendix B.

Maddalena, Italy

The 9 SAR scenes acquired for this test site have been calibrated and wind retrieved. The CMOD-IFR2 requires input wind direction to calculate wind speed from the SAR imagery. First, the input wind direction was obtained from the in situ measurements. The all the wind maps were re-calculated in order to obtain wind direction directly from the SAR imagery whenever possible (when wind streaks are present). The data are described in Table 4. In situ measurements are taken from the offshore Mezzo-Passo anemometer and SAR wind (for comparison) taken from a box east of the in situ measurements. The Meteorological station Mezzo Passo is a 10 m off-shore tower situated in the narrow strait between Sardinia mainland and the Maddalena Island. Wind measurements are available as 10-min. mean speeds for the period January 1997 – June 1999.

Table 4. Maddalena data.

*In situ wind from offshore-Mezzo Passo anemometer data at 10 m height (Latitude 41°12'. Longitude 9°21')

** Wind direction taken directly from SAR image whenever possible (FFT techniques), otherwise measured offshore Mezzo-Passo wind direction is used.

(Wdir is always given relative to north).

No.	Date	Time	Orbit	Frame	Wdir insitu [deg.]*	WS insitu [m/s]*
1	21-05-97	2137	10905	0819	246.5	11.97
2	31-05-97	1006	11041	2781	88.9	9.09
3	18-10-97	1006	13045	2781	79.3	8.3
4	22-11-97	1006	13546	2781	18.8	8.32
5	27-12-97	1006	14047	2781	284.4	15.87
6	11-04-98	1006	15550	2781	216.6	9.99
7	06-05-98	2137	15915	0819	256	8.04
8	25-07-98	1006	17053	2781	263.2	11.26
9	12-12-98	1006	19057	2781	18.38	8.09

The SAR wind maps are collected on a CD-Rom labelled WEMSAR-Deliverable D3. The wind maps are shown in Appendix C.

Gulf of Suez, Egypt

The 5 SAR scenes acquired for this test site have been calibrated and wind retrieved. The CMOD-IFR2 requires input wind direction to calculate wind speed from the SAR imagery. First, the input wind direction was obtained from the in situ measurements. The all the wind maps were re-calculated in order to obtain wind direction directly from the SAR imagery

whenever possible (when wind streaks are present). The data are described in Table 5. In situ measurements are taken from differernt in situ measurements near the SAR images.

Table 5. Gulf of Suez data.

In situ wind from:

- **HU (Hurghada WETC):** WS: 10m and 24.5m height, Wdir:24m height (Latitude xx°xx'. Longitude x°xx')
- **ZA (Zafarana):** WS: 24.5m height, Wdir: 24m height (Latitude 29°16.8'. Longitude 32°36.6')
- **DA (Abu Darag):** WS: 24.5m height, Wdir: 24m height (Latitude xx°xx'. Longitude x°xx')
- **EL (Gulf of El-Zayt):** WS: 24.5m height, Wdir: 24m height (Latitude xx°xx'. Longitude x°xx')

(Wdir is always given relative to north).

No.	DATE	Time	ORBIT	FRAME	Wdir.- insitu	WS- insitu	COMMENTS
1	960405	2011	05021	0585	1	15.74	I-PAF, DA
2	960405b	2010	05021	0549	305	5.30	I-PAF, EL
3	960405c	2010	05021	0567	20	18.83	I-PAF, ZA
4	991002	2007	42959	0549	237	3.70 4.46	I-PAF, HU
5	991110	2013	23830	0567	256		I-PAF, ZA
6	991110b	2013	23830	0549	256		I-PAF, ZA

Image number 6 contains mostly land, and wind was therefore not extracted.

WP2.2. Validation of SAR wind – Deliverable 4 (D4)

Hellisøy, Norway

The validation results for Hellisøy presented here, are partially published in Furevik and Espedal (2001) shown in appendix D.

The weather station on Hellisøy is situated on top of a 10 m high mast mounted in connection with a house, and is further surrounded by several other masts and buildings and a very rough terrain which all have impact on the wind climate (Figure 1). The anemometer measures wind at 33 m above sea level and records the average wind speed over ten minutes every hour. The speed-up effect caused by the terrain will vary for the different wind directions and may be considerable under certain conditions (Jackson and Hunt, 1975). Presently we have no models available to correct for these conditions in the Hellisøy data, and therefore we can not expect that a comparison between the ocean wind measurements provided by the SAR and the *in situ* measurements will show very good agreement. However, in a preliminary study, the main characteristics of the wind field will be represented by the *in situ* data.

Figure 1. a) Map of the North Sea region showing the study area on the west coast of Norway. b) The geographical position of Hellisøy where *in situ* wind measurements were taken. c) Photograph of Hellisøy (from east) showing the position of the mast from which the wind data were obtained (arrow).

The wind extracted from the SAR scenes are averaged over a $10 \text{ km} \times 10 \text{ km}$ region (white box, Plate 6) and compared with measurements from Hellisøy and the ECMWF data for all available days. It was possible to derive wind directions from 22 of the 50 scenes and these agree very well with the directions observed at Hellisøy and from the ECMWF (Figure 2). The wind speed values are somewhat scattered and underestimate for high wind speeds compared to the *in situ* data (Figure 3a, 40 data points). We interpret this as being mainly due to a speed-up effect over the island, as discussed earlier. The SAR retrieved wind speed values are found to agree better with the wind from the ECMWF analysis (10 m above sea level) extracted offshore at $60.5^\circ\text{N} \times 4.5^\circ\text{E}$ (Figure 3b, 28 data points). This may confirm the hypothesis of a speed-up effect at the Hellisøy lighthouse station.

There is one data point where the SAR retrieved wind is very low (1.2 m/s) while both Hellisøy and ECMWF data indicates relatively high winds of 6.6 m/s and 9.2 m/s, respectively. This point refers to a situation from early summer with offshore winds. As the warm air (about $+18^\circ\text{C}$) from land moves offshore over the relatively cold sea surface, an internal boundary layer seems to develop which keeps the air flow from interacting with the sea surface (Kaimal and Finnigan, 1994). This gives low wind conditions in the wind field retrieved from SAR.

Figure 2. a) Comparison of SAR derived wind directions (averaged within a $10\text{km} \times 10\text{km}$ region) against wind direction from Hellisøy lighthouse (10min. average). b) Comparison of SAR wind direction against ECMWF wind direction.

Figure 3. (a) Comparison between SAR derived wind speed against in-situ (40 data points), and (b) ECMWF (28 data points) wind speed. When possible, input wind direction was taken from SAR (Black dots). For the remaining cases, Hellisøy wind direction was used (white dots).

Horns Rev, Denmark

The validation for the Horns Rev test site is described in WEMSAR Report No.3, by Risoe.

Maddalena, Italy

The Meteorological station Mezzo Passo is a 10 m off-shore tower situated in the narrow strait between Sardinia main-land and the Maddalena Island (Figure 4). Wind measurements are available as 10-min. mean speeds for the period January 1997 – June 1999. Comparison between SAR retrieved wind speed and direction for the 9 SAR images obtained for this test site thus far, are shown in Figure 5.

The two points in Figure 5b which are near 360° in wind direction, should have been plotted as 0° . The wind directions from SAR are in fairly good agreement with in situ measurements from Mezzo Passo. The SAR wind speed values differ somewhat from in situ measurements. This can be explained by the location of the in situ measurement station (in between some islands, Figure 4).

Figure 4. Map indicating the location of the Maddalena test site. In situ measurements were obtained from the meteorological station (photo), location indicated by an arrow.

Figure 5. Comparison between SAR wind and in-situ wind at the Maddalena test site, speed (a) and direction (b).

Conclusion

The preliminary comparison between SAR, in-situ measurements and some model results show promising results. The SAR is seen to provide useful wind speed maps. Ongoing validation work includes comparing SAR wind speed offshore, against computed wind speed using the WasP model to calculate the offshore wind based on the in situ on-land wind measurements from Hellisøy and Mezzo Passo.

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Appendices

Appendix A: SAR wind maps, Hellisøy

The SAR wind maps are collected on a CD-Rom labelled WEMSAR-Deliverable D3. The wind maps are shown below.

Plate 1

Plate 2

Plate 3

Plate 4

Plate 5

Plate 6

Plate 7

Appendix B, Horns Rev

The SAR wind maps are collected on a CD-Rom labelled WEMSAR-Deliverable D3. The wind maps are shown in below.

Plate 8

Plate 9

Plate 10

Appendix C, Maddalena, Italy

The SAR wind maps are collected on a CD-Rom labelled WEMSAR-Deliverable D3. The wind maps are shown below.

Plate 11

Plate 12

Appendix D, Paper

Wind energy mapping using Synthetic Aperture Radar

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Wind energy mapping using Synthetic Aperture Radar

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Abstract:

Offshore and coastal wind farms are becoming important sources of renewable energy. The energy production of a wind farm is closely connected to its location, and the expected outcome is traditionally calculated from at least one year of accurate wind measurements. Satellite SAR wind mapping may become a useful tool in the process of selecting the optimal site for these measurements, and may therefore increase the cost effectiveness when planning wind farms. The study described in this paper is based on 28 SAR scenes from the Norwegian west coast near the town of Bergen. The wind fields retrieved from these images have been compared with *in situ* wind data from the Hellisøy lighthouse and modelled wind from the European Centre for Medium-range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). Based on long-term wind information from the lighthouse, the SAR scenes that show the most representative wind conditions for the site were chosen for the study. The data give an overview of the spatial distribution of the wind field in this coastal region. According to the SAR data, the area with the highest wind energy potential lies in the area north of Hellisøy in the mouth of Sognefjord, as this area is open for most wind directions.

INTRODUCTION

Wind power is a growing industry important for exploitation of renewable energy sources. Such exploitation is necessary to reduce consumption of fossil fuel, which has a severe impact on the global climate. The dominant energy source in Norway is hydropower, representing 99% of the total electricity consumption. However, there is a growing interest in the exploitation of wind energy, as less than one sixth of the total hydropower potential remains for exploitation, and further growth in energy consumption in Norway requires use of other energy sources. In Denmark where wind power is the main natural power resource, wind turbines provided 8.6% of the total electricity consumption in 1998 (Lemming and Andersen, 1999). The energy production from wind farms was 2779GWh from a total of more than 5200 wind turbines, most of them sited on land. The Danish wind industry has been build up over about 30 years, receiving large subsidies from the government. The turbines become increasingly effective in converting energy from the wind to electricity and production costs are reduced, making wind farms competitive in the energy market. Offshore sites are now becoming more interesting due to higher energy potential and less frequent conflicts with environmental considerations and other interests. The foundation of the turbines can be placed in water depths of up to 20m, which are found in many coastal waters of Denmark. In Norway, however, the wind turbines in most cases must be sited on land as there are few off-shore areas with shallow water.

Wind farms can also be important to meet energy demands in developing countries where the infrastructure for power distribution is limited. In these regions, SAR derived wind information can potentially play an important role for planning installations, regardless of a lack of *in situ* observations and inaccessible areas.

In the planning of wind farm locations, wind statistics from available long-term meteorological weather stations are analyzed to obtain the dominant wind directions and speeds for the site. Furthermore, the wind climatology for a potential site is thoroughly studied for a minimum of one year by taking accurate meteorological measurements. These data are then used as input to energy calculations and mathematical flow models. At this stage it is possible to create a detailed map of the spatial energy distribution for the site. By use of remote sensing in the planning phase of a wind farm, it is possible to obtain wind energy maps with high spatial resolution at an early stage (Johannessen and Bjørge, 2000).

The most appropriate remote sensing method for high-resolution wind measurements is Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR). Using a C-band algorithm such as the CMOD-IFR2 (Quilfen *et al.*, 1998) the wind speed can be retrieved from ERS SAR scenes with an accuracy of ± 1.5 m/s compared to *in situ* measurements in the open ocean (Vachon and Dobson, 1996). This accuracy is similar to the wind estimates from ERS Wind Scatterometer (WSC) providing global ocean wind fields with 50km resolution used operationally in weather forecast models (Homleid and Breivik, 1995; Tomassini *et al.*, 1998). However, WSC data are too coarse for near-coastal observation of the wind field. The main benefit of the SAR is thus the high spatial resolution (~30m for ERS SAR), making it possible to retrieve wind fields in near coastal regions (Korsbakken *et al.*, 1998; Lehner *et al.*, 1998). With regular acquisition of SAR data over a given site, i.e. every 1- to 3 days, temporal as well as spatial statistics from the SAR data will become available. This is possible with combined use of SAR systems from different satellites. Mapping of wind fields by RADARSAT-1 ScanSAR imagery (100m resolution) has already been demonstrated for larger coastal regions (Horstmann *et al.*, 2000; Monaldo, 2000; Vachon *et al.*, 2000).

The objective of this study is to investigate the potential of using satellite SAR data in siting offshore/coastal wind farms. For the first time, a description of SAR retrieved wind fields in the context of wind turbine siting is given. From the data set of 28 ERS SAR precision (PRI) scenes, the five most representative situations for the Norwegian west coast are chosen, based on the wind rose from Hellisøy lighthouse. The retrieved wind fields are discussed in terms of general patterns in coastal wind field and regions with high wind energy potential. It is demonstrated that the retrieved wind fields give an overview of the offshore wind energy potential in the area covered, and can act as a supplement to existing mast data and numerical model output in the process of selecting an optimal site for a wind farm. Data description, methodology and a comparison of the available data is given in the following section. Then the chosen scenes are presented and discussed, and finally some conclusions are given.

WIND EXTRACTION FROM SAR AND COMPARISON WITH GROUND TRUTH DATA

Using the SAR toolbox (available online at: <http://earth.esa.int/STBX/>), 28 ERS SAR PRI scenes have been calibrated in order to obtain optimal wind speed estimates from the empirical C-band model. The wind speed in this study was retrieved from the normalised radar backscatter cross section using the CMOD-IFR2 algorithm developed at the Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer, Brest, France (IFREMER). This algorithm is empirically tuned to buoy measurements and is used operationally for retrieval of wind fields from the ERS Wind Scatterometer (WSC). Investigations have shown that in contrast to the SAR Wind Algorithm (SWA) using azimuth cut-off (Vachon *et al.*, 1994), the SAR wind speed estimates using C-band models appear not to be affected to the same degree by fetch-limited sea. However, the atmospheric conditions and surface film presence may affect the results (Kerbaol *et al.*, 1998; Korsbakken *et al.*, 1998). The CMOD-IFR2 is developed for

neutral stability and errors will therefore be introduced in SAR wind speed estimates if conditions are unstable or stable. Atmospheric conditions are also important for the interaction of the air flow with the topography. On days with low-level temperature inversion, the air can be forced around topographical obstacles and generate jets and gap winds in certain localities (Pan and Smith, 1999; Sandvik and Furevik, 2001). While on other days the flow can receive a speed-up effect from the topography, giving higher wind speeds at the top of hills. Unfortunately, no temperature profiles are available to investigate this further in the data set presented here.

The SAR wind speeds are retrieved for a pixel size of $400\text{m} \times 400\text{m}$, as wind information for use in coastal areas must be of high spatial resolution, and the quality of such data must be validated. Wind speed estimates from SAR are comparable to the WSC wind speeds, and the spatial variability in the SAR estimates only increases slightly with higher resolution (down to a pixel size of $500\text{ m} \times 500\text{ m}$) compared to the coarse WSC estimates (Furevik and Korsbakken, 2000). However, between $500\text{ m} \times 500\text{ m}$ to $200\text{ m} \times 200\text{ m}$ in pixel size the variability of the SAR retrieved winds increased significantly. Korsbakken *et al.* (1998) show plots for the mean values of SAR retrieved wind in sub-images around a ship position for varying sub-image size (100m to 10km). In this study it was concluded that the SAR winds did not change significantly with the sub-image area size. Profiles drawn in SAR wind maps of $400\text{ m} \times 400\text{ m}$ pixel size, do not show sign of speckle when compared to ship track data (Furevik *et al.*, 2001).

A disadvantage of SAR wind retrievals using C-band models is the requirement for wind direction as an input to the algorithm. For the present study we have used the FFT technique (Gerling, 1986; Vachon and Dobson, 1996). The SAR scene is divided into 8×8 sub-images from which the image spectra are derived using two-dimensional FFT. From the direction of the peaks in the long

wavelength part of the spectrum (wavelengths longer than 1500 m) wind directions with an ambiguity of 180° are estimated. The peaks in an image spectrum are orthogonal to the wind streaks often observed in SAR data. Wind streaks are surface manifestations of atmospheric roll vortices or Langmuir cells, and are aligned with the local wind direction (Alpers and Brummer, 1994; Brown, 1980). The ambiguity in the wind direction estimate is solved by the use of weather maps or *in situ* data. The estimated wind direction in the sub-images are interpolated to the whole scene and used as input to the CMOD-IFR2. In the cases where a wind direction was retrieved in less than three of the 64 sub-images, the wind direction from Hellisøy was used. The accuracy of the FFT technique is estimated to about 20° in the cases where wind streaks are present (Vachon and Dobson, 1996). For a given error in wind direction, the largest error in wind speed is found for high radar return. However, for strong winds the variation in local wind direction is small, and in almost all these cases wind streaks are present in the SAR scenes. For 23° incidence angle of the ERS SAR, an error in wind direction of 50° for a backscatter value of -6dB would result in an error in wind speed of up to 3 m/s in the CMOD-IFR2 algorithm (depending on wind direction relative to the satellite flight direction).

The resulting wind speed matrices can be transformed into matrices of wind energy (energy flux) by applying the bulk formula (see e.g. a basic physics book such as Marion and Hornyak, 1982):

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \rho_{air} V^3, \quad (1)$$

where E [W/m²] is the energy flux, ρ_{air} [kg/m³] is the density of the air and V [m/s] is the wind speed. The density for dry air is 1.225 kg/m³ at standard pressure and a temperature of 15°C. From this relation it is clear that low wind speeds contribute very little to wind energy relative to medium and high wind speeds. For very high wind speeds, the rotor blades risk being damaged due to turbulence

and the turbines are normally switched off. However, for technical design of the wind turbines, knowledge of extreme/very high winds is required since the turbines have to withstand these winds. In the working range of the wind turbines, high winds give most wind energy. However, these events are more seldom (low frequency of occurrence), and therefore medium winds are usually the most important for wind energy production.

Figure 1. Map of the North Sea region (a) showing the study area on the west coast of Norway. b) The geographical position of Hellisøy where *in situ* wind measurements were taken. c) Photograph of Hellisøy (from east) showing the position of the mast from which the wind data were obtained (arrow).

The weather station on Hellisøy is situated on top of a 10 m high mast mounted in connection with a house, and is further surrounded by several other masts and buildings and a very rough terrain which all have impact on the wind climate (**Figure 1**). The anemometer measures wind at 33 m above sea

level and records the average wind speed over ten minutes every hour. The speed-up effect caused by the terrain will vary for the different wind directions and may be considerable under certain conditions (Jackson and Hunt, 1975). Presently we have no models available to correct for these conditions in the Hellisøy data, and therefore we can not expect that a comparison between the ocean wind measurements provided by the SAR and the *in situ* measurements will show very good agreement. However, in this preliminary study, the main characteristics of the wind field will be represented by the *in situ* data.

Based on measurements during 1993-1998 the wind rose in **Figure 2a**, was calculated. The wind speed intervals are given in Beaufort [B] and the wind directions were binned into eight 45° intervals. In addition, a second wind rose from Hellisøy (**Figure 2b**) based on 2 years of data (1996-1997) indicates the relative wind energy potential for the different wind directions (red).

Figure 2. a) Wind rose from Hellisøy lighthouse, based on data from 1993-1998 (source: DNMI Norway). Wind speed intervals are given in Beaufort [B] (3-4 B = 3-8 m/s, 5-6 B = 8-14 m/s). The most typical wind direction is from the south (157.5°-202.5°), which occurred

21.5% of the time. The most typical wind speed range for that wind direction is 8-14 m/s. b) Wind rose from Hellisøy lighthouse based on data from 1996 and 1997. The same pattern is seen as in a) with highest frequency (in percent) of winds from south, north and south-east (blue). The mean wind speed in the bins times the frequency of occurrence for the bin is plotted in black. The wind speed to the third (wind energy) times the occurrence frequency is plotted in red. At Hellisøy, the high wind speeds occur most frequent for southerly winds.

The wind extracted from the SAR scenes are averaged over a $10 \text{ km} \times 10 \text{ km}$ region (white box, **Figure 4**) and compared with measurements from Hellisøy and the ECMWF data for all available days (**Figure 3**). It was possible to derive wind directions from 13 of the 28 scenes and these agree very well with the directions observed at Hellisøy (**Figure 3b**). The wind speed values are somewhat scattered and underestimate for high wind speeds compared to the *in situ* data (**Figure 3a**). We interpret this as being mainly due to a speed-up effect over the island, as discussed earlier. The SAR retrieved wind speed values are found to agree better with the wind from the ECMWF analysis (10 m above sea level) extracted offshore at $60.5^\circ\text{N} \times 4.5^\circ\text{E}$ (**Figure 3c,d**). This may confirm the hypothesis of a speed-up effect at the Hellisøy lighthouse station.

There is one data point where the SAR retrieved wind is very low (1.2 m/s) while both Hellisøy and ECMWF data indicates relatively high winds of 6.6 m/s and 9.2 m/s, respectively. This point refers to a situation from early summer with offshore winds. As the warm air (about $+18^\circ\text{C}$) from land moves offshore over the relatively cold sea surface, an internal boundary layer seems to develop which keeps the air flow from interacting with the sea surface (Kaimal and Finnigan, 1994). This gives low wind conditions in the wind field retrieved from SAR.

a)

b)

c)

d)

Figure 3. a) Comparison of wind speed from Hellisøy lighthouse (10 min. average) with SAR retrieved wind speed using CMOD-IFR2 (averaged within a $10 \text{ km} \times 10 \text{ km}$ region shown in **Figure 4**). When possible, input wind direction was taken from SAR (Black dots). For the remaining cases, Hellisøy wind direction was used (white dots). b) Comparison of wind direction from Hellisøy with SAR derived wind directions. c), d) Comparison of SAR data with ECMWF data for both wind speed and direction. Black and white dots; same as in a). Linear regression (dashed lines) are for all data points.

To investigate possible benefits from SAR in offshore/coastal wind turbine siting, images from our SAR archive were selected for cases of typical wind speeds and directions. The SAR images were then studied together with the *in situ* data from Hellisøy and ECMWF analysis to provide wind fields and wind energy maps with a spatial resolution of 400 m × 400 m.

SAR WIND ESTIMATES FOR THE NORWEGIAN WEST COAST

The most typical wind directions were selected from the wind rose for Hellisøy (**Figure 2**). The five dominant wind directions are south (occurring 21.5% of the time), south-east (17.9%), north (17.5%), north-west (11.3%) and south-west (10.6%). The SAR scene chosen to represent southerly winds is from 17 August 1997, covering Fedje/Hellisøy, the surrounding islands and fjords and some open sea (**Figure 4**). A large low north of Iceland caused moderate south-westerly winds in the North Sea. The wind speed at the west coast of Norway was too low for the air to proceed over the mountains and thus the wind turned to south and followed the coast. The SAR acquisition time was 10:49UTC, and the *in situ* data were logged at 11:00 UTC. The SAR retrieved wind speed (5.5 m/s) near Hellisøy is lower than the measured wind speed of 7.6 m/s. Approximately 10-15 km off-shore the wind speed is generally higher by about 3-4m/s. This becomes very pronounced in the wind energy maps (**Figure 4b**) derived from using Equation 1. A profile from the coast to the open sea (**Figure 4c**) indicates 50% higher wind energy potential offshore for this situation. Note that wind speeds less than 6 m/s give very little input to the wind energy distribution.

Figure 4. a) SAR wind speed map from 970817 with winds from the south (occurrence frequency of 21.5%). In this case no wind features in the SAR image could indicate the wind direction field, and the measured value from Hellisøy (180°) was therefore used (arrows). At Hellisøy, an average wind speed of 7.6 m/s was measured, and the ECMWF data indicated a wind of 6.0 m/s. The white box shows the position of the 10 km × 10 km region where SAR winds are extracted for **Table 1** and the comparison in **Figure 3**. b) Wind energy [W/m^2] derived from the SAR wind speed map using Equation 1. c) The profile displaying wind energy along a line from Hellisøy towards the open sea. There is a clear trend of higher wind energy away from the coast.

To represent the other dominant wind directions for Hellisøy, SAR scenes from November 10, 1996, June 22 and 23, 1996, and July 27, 1996 (**Figure 5**) were chosen. The example for south-easterly winds (**Figure 5a**) unfortunately is a low wind case which is seen from the dark patches in the south.

The average SAR wind speed within the 10 km × 10 km box is 6.1 m/s, which is in agreement with the measured wind speed at Hellisøy at 11:00 UTC (**Table 1**). In the mouth of Sognefjord/Fensfjord, the wind speed is about 8 m/s. The SAR scene representing northerly winds (**Figure 5b**), is a high wind speed case from June 22, 1996 (14.7m/s at Hellisøy) related to a low over southern Sweden. A wavy pattern is seen over the open sea that might be related to atmospheric gravity waves (Vachon *et al.*, 1995). This pattern is still present on the following day when the wind has turned to the north-west (**Figure 5c**) and slowed to about 4-5 m/s on average. An enhanced wind speed of about 7 m/s is found in the fjords parallel to the wind direction and somewhat higher winds are also found offshore. The SAR scene representing south-westerly winds (**Figure 5d**) is covering a medium strong wind situation (9.5 m/s at Hellisøy) giving another example of reduced wind speed when approaching the coast as was also seen in **Figure 5c** for north-westerly winds and in **Figure 4** for southerly winds.

In general, for wind directions along the coast and offshore flow there is a tendency for higher wind speed in the fjords orientated approximately parallel to the wind direction where no mountains are blocking the flow. Therefore we would recommend an area open for the dominant southerly winds and at the mouth of a fjord for investigation of wind energy potential using the traditional methods with mast recordings and model simulations. For our specific area we find that the mouth of Sognefjord/Fensfjord north of Fedje (**Figure 1**) seems to be the area most useful for wind energy. This area is open for the dominant southerly wind direction (through Hjeltefjord) and south-easterly winds (through Fensfjord) in addition to all westerly wind directions, and the less frequent north-easterly winds (through Sognefjord). In this area there are many islands on which to place masts and turbines.

a) 961110 with winds from the south-east (frequency of occurrence: 17.9%).

b) 960622 with winds from the north (frequency of occurrence: 17.5%).

c) 960623 with winds from the north-west (frequency of occurrence: 11.3%).

d) 960727 with winds from south-west (frequency of occurrence: 10.6%).

Figure 5. Scenes representing four of the dominant wind directions for the Hellisøy lighthouse weather station. The related *in situ* measurements for the scenes can be found in **Table 1**. Arrows indicate the wind direction while the colour code represents wind speed [m/s].

Table 1. Wind from SAR, Hellisøy and ECMWF data analysis for the five scenes shown in **Figure 4** and **Figure 5**. For August, 17, 1997, no wind direction features were seen in the

SAR images, and the input to CMOD-IFR2 was taken from the Hellisøy data. Wind speed values from Hellisøy are averaged over 10 minutes (mean), and the maximum is the highest value for a 6-hour period. The average and maximum wind from the SAR was extracted from a 10km × 10km box in the open sea to the west of Hellisøy (see **Figure 4**). ECMWF data were extracted at 60.5°N × 4.5°E.

Date	ERS SAR			Observations at Hellisøy			ECMWF data	
	Time (UTC)	WS [m/s] (10m a.s.l.) mean/max	Wind dir. [deg.]	Time (UTC)	WS [m/s] (33m a.s.l.) mean/max	Wind dir. [deg.]	WS [m/s] (10m a.s.l.)	Wind dir. [deg.]
970817	10:49	5.5/9.2	-	11:00	7.6/10.3	180	6.0	174
961110	10:49	6.1/7.5	147	11:00	6.1/8.0	113	5.5	201
960622	10:49	10.3/11.1	349	11:00	14.7/19.4	339	7.3	355
960623	10:49	4.3/4.8	328	11:00	8.5/10.3	321	5.7	341
960727	10:49	7.0/7.1	229	11:00	9.3/ 10.3	234	7.0	199

a.s.l.: above sea level.

CONCLUSIONS

The ideal situation for wind energy mapping is to use the SAR imagery to retrieve the spatial variation of the probability density function of the wind speed. However, this cannot be retrieved from the limited number of SAR scenes used in this study. Therefore, local meteorological data are used to find days with dominant wind directions and speeds. SAR scenes acquired on days representing these wind conditions will then give examples of spatial wind variations that are typical for the area. These data can aid in selecting a region for further investigations, such as where to place a local weather mast. Through the comparison of the available data it is seen that the *in situ* data seems to be affected by local conditions, and there is a need for methods to help to extend the validity of the ground truth data to a larger area.

It is well known that the wind speed over the open sea is generally higher than near the shore, and this is also observed in most of the SAR retrieved wind fields. An exception occurs in some cases when the wind direction is near parallel to the length direction of the fjords. Based on the five SAR scenes chosen for this demonstration, wind conditions are generally found to be favourable at the islands in the mouth of Sognefjord/Fensfjord. This region seems to have the highest potential for wind energy production, and detailed wind measurements should be carried out here. To be able to decide exactly on which island measurements should be started, the high-resolution wind fields should be investigated in combination with knowledge of the local infrastructure and area regulations.

In coastal areas the land-sea air circulation can contribute significantly to the local wind energy potential. This diurnal variation generally cannot be seen in ERS SAR images, due to the satellite orbit which is descending at approximately 10:50UTC and ascending at 21:30UTC for Hellisøy (+1 hour for local time). Note that other SARs, such as RADARSAT-1, have a dawn-dusk orbit. The evening pass might catch the onset of the land breeze, while the sea breeze in the early afternoon will not be imaged at all. The SAR offers spatial measurements of the wind at high resolution, acting as a supplement to traditional information, which is often *in situ* data (from point sources) and mathematical modelling. With regular acquisition of SAR data over a given site, i.e. every 1- to 3 days, it will be possible to build up temporal statistics from the SAR data in addition to the spatial statistics. With combined use of two wide-swath SAR systems such as RADARSAT-1(2) and ENVISAT ASAR, and reduced data cost, it will be possible to improve the temporal as well as spatial coverage, which is needed in order to obtain such statistics.

In a recent European Commission (EC) project "Wind energy mapping using synthetic aperture radar (WEMSAR)", the possibilities for using SAR wind energy mapping for offshore siting of wind farms

will be studied further (see Johannessen *et al.* 2000; Hasager *et al.*, 2001). The key innovation in the project is in focusing recent advances in remote sensing research into a system that will improve understanding of the usefulness of SAR, and aid potential customers to use this technology for maximum wind information retrieval. The system is expected to be particularly valuable in remote coastal areas, where the wind measurements are sparse and there is a need for local production of electric power.

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